

Contraceptive Choices Among Urban Slum and Rural Women: A Comparative Study

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ABSTRACT

Although India is the first country in the world to launch the National Family Welfare Program in 1952. It is disheartening that we are still lagging behind and not yet achieved the desired global standards in birth control methods utilization. Among all the health programs in India, the Family welfare program is identified as a prime concern area, and it is fully being executed as a centrally sponsored program. As per 1996 census five states i.e. Bihar, Uttar Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Rajasthan and Orissa contributed 44% of the whole population of India and it further increased to 48% in 2016. The fertility remains very high in most of the northern and central states. The contraceptive usage among these states is relatively lower than the southern and western states and it's predicted that these states will contribute 55% of total population in future. The aim of the study was to assess the preferred choice of contraceptive method among married women residing in urban slum and rural area of Bhopal city. Cross sectional study was conducted among married women for a period of two months (November- December 2015) with sample size of 196 married women, in urban training health Centre Indrapuri (Bhopal) and Rural training health Centre Ratua (Bhopal). Findings indicate that majority of participants (42%) and (22.92%) adopted permanent method in rural and urban slum area respectively. (77.08%) and (58%) adopted temporary method in Urban slum and rural area respectively. Majority of participants (47.92%) preferred condom, (16.66%) preferred Mala-D, (12.5%) preferred copper - T in urban slum area. Whereas (30%) preferred condom, (15%) preferred mala-D, and (12%) preferred copper -T in rural area.

KEY WORDS: contraceptive methods, married women, preferred choice, urban slum

INTRODUCTION:

Over a quarter of India's population lives below the poverty line. 80% of the population lives on less than two dollars a day.^[1] It is well known that living condition in India is amongst the poorer nations of the world. India's population growth rate is 1.74% and the total fertility rate is 2.85%. Every Fifth birth in the world is an Indian, and 50% of the Indian population is of reproductive age.^[2]

India is having 1.27 billion people, with this number of population it becomes second most populated country in the world, whereas the China is

one of the topmost with over 1.36 billion peoples^[3]. 26.8% of the girls get married below the age of 18 years in India. Out of the total birth in India 10.7% become mother at the age of 15-19 year. Most of the population about 72.2% lives in 6, 38,000 villages and remaining 27.8% in about 5480 towns and urban agglomeration. If the birth control methods utilization rate will not increase in future, the population will increase from 1210 million in 2011 to 1400 million in 2026 by estimated increase rate in population growth 15.7% in next fifteen years and India become most populated country in world with highest no of population.^[4]

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MATERIALS AND METHODS

This quantitative study was a comparative non experimental study done to assess the preferred choice of contraceptive methods among married women residing in urban slum and rural area of Bhopal city. The study was approved by Research Advisory

committee and Institutional Ethics Committee of Peoples College of Nursing and Research Centre, Bhopal. Study was conducted from November 2015 to December 2015 at Ratua and 60 quarters in Indrapuri Bhopal. Ratua is rural area and 60 Quarter is urban slum area of Bhopal. Total 196 married women were selected through non probability purposive sampling technique, 96 women from urban health training centre and 100 women from rural health training centre. The women who were participated in the study met the inclusion and exclusion criteria.

After selecting the participants explained them about the study. Written consent was obtained from the study participants. After obtaining the consent from the participant's self-structured questionnaire was used to collect the data.

Self-structured questionnaire consist of total three sections. Section one comprise socio demographic data, section two consist questions related to family planning and section three consist questions related to preferred choice of contraceptive methods.

Collected data were compiled and analyzed with using SPSS statistical software by statistician. Result were explained as frequency and percentage distribution of socio demographic data and preferred choice of contraceptive methods. Chi square was used to find out the association between preferred choice of contraceptive with socio demographic variable of study participants $p < 0.05$ was considered as significant level.

RESULTS:

The findings of the study revealed that majority of participants 45.9% and 60% belonged to age group of 18 – 27 year in urban slum and rural area. 49% were illiterate in urban slum area and 30% had middle class education in rural area. 69%, 51% belonged to nuclear family in urban slum and rural area respectively. Twenty five percentage (25%) and 26% had two children in urban slum and rural area, 33%, 56% had more than two children in urban slum and rural area. Fifty four percentage (54%) participants duration of marriage were 4 - 8 year in urban slum area and 52% participants duration of marriage were 9-11 years in rural area.

Majority of participants 42% adopted permanent method and 58% adopted temporary method in rural area. 22.92% adopted permanent method and 77.08% adopted temporary method in urban slum area. Majority of participants 42% preferred condom 30% preferred Mala – D, 15%

preferred copper –T in rural area. 47.9% preferred condom 16.6% preferred Mala D and 12.5% were preferred Copper – T and in urban slum area (Table 1 & Table 2). This study showed significant association between preferred choice of contraceptive method and socio-demographic variable like age, education, type of family, no of children, years of marriage, and family income. Whereas there is no significant association found between preferred choice of contraceptive method with their sociodemographic variables like occupation and residential area.

DISCUSSION:

Preferred choice of contraceptives can be temporary (contraception) or permanent (sterilization). Contraceptive methods are those methods which help women to avoid unwanted pregnancies and spacing between two births.^[5] In this study preferred choice of contraceptive method in both urban slum and rural were found permanent method of contraception, mainly female sterilization. The study findings were supported by Vaidyanathan Anjana et al cross sectional study also revealed that the permanent method of contraception specifically female sterilization was the top most preferred method of contraception in both urban and rural areas.^[2]

Further in temporary method of contraception male condom (47.92% and 30%) was preferred choice of contraception both in urban slum and rural area. whereas study done by SS Prateek et al indicated that Cu-T (41.37%) was most preferred method of contraception in urban area^[6] and Reddy Rajesh S et al study depicted that the condoms were the most preferred (54%) temporary method among study participants^[7].

Table (2) association between preferred choice of contraceptive method with socio-demographic factors show that women aged between 18-27 were more likely to preferred permanent method after having there or four children's in rural area and who had using temporary method they preferred condom and mala –D as compare to Cu –T.

Women aged 28-37 years were preferred to use condom for contraception as compared to Cu-T and Mala-D. On the other hand women aged between 38-47 year were preferred to use Cu-T and Mala-D as contraceptive method. Women who were illiterate preferred condom as contraceptive methods where as women having higher secondary education were likely to preferred Mala-D compare to Cu-T and condom as contraceptive method in urban slum area.

Table 1: Preferred Method of Contraceptive among married women Residing In Urban slum and Rural Areas (n=196).

Preferred method of contraceptive	Urban Slum		Rural		Total	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Permanent method	22	22.92	42	42%	64	32.65
Condom	46	47.92	30	30%	76	38.78
Mala-D	16	16.66	15	15%	31	15.82
Copper -T	12	12.5	13	13%	25	12.75

Table 2: Association between preferred choice of contraceptive method with their socio-demographic variables (n= 196).

Demographic	Frequency	Item	X ²	P-value	Significant
Age					
18-27 year	105	Condom	59.520	<0.0001	Significant
28-37 year	50	Mala – D			
38-47 year	41	Copper – T			
Education					
Illiterate	58	Condom	145.428	<0.0001	Significant
Middle	66	Mala – D			
Primary	33	Copper – T			
Higher Secondary	37				
Graduate	2				
Type of Family					
Nuclear	120	Condom	50.954	<0.0001	Significant
Joint	60	Mala – D			
		Copper – T			
Occupation					
Housewife	171	Condom	15.291	0.018	Not Significant
Government job	10	Mala – D			
Private job	15	Copper – T			
Area of living					
Rural	100	Condom	9.613	0.022	Not Significant
Urban	96	Mala – D			
		Copper – T			
No. of Children					
One	44	Condom	88.974	<0.0001	Significant
Two	48	Mala – D			
More Than Two	88	Copper – T			
None	16				
Year of Marriage					
Below 3 year	14	Condom	110.961	<0.0001	Significant
4-8 year	90	Mala – D			
9-15 year	80	Copper – T			
16-22 year	2				
23-40 year	10				
Family Income					
Below Rs.5000	35	Condom	90.217	<0.0001	Significant
Rs.5001 -10000	89	Mala – D			
Rs.10001 -15000	13	Copper – T			
More than Rs.15000	59				

Whereas women had middle class education were used permanent method of contraception after having three or more children in rural area. According to the Ochaklo Rhouné et al cross sectional study revealed that women having secondary and higher education were preferred traditional short term methods^[8].

Women residing in nuclear family were mostly preferred condom and Cu-T for contraception as compare to Mala-D in both the urban slum and rural area. Women with one child were likely preferred condom and Mala-D as preferred choice of contraceptive method both in urban slum and rural area.

In this study women with 4-8 years duration of marriage preferably like to use Mala-D for contraception as compare to women who had 9-17 years duration of marriage both in urban slum and rural area. Women belong income group of Rs 5001-10,000 were like to preferred condom and Cu-T for contraception compared to Mala-D in both the urban slum and rural area.

In this study researcher compare the preferred choice of contraceptive method between urban slum and rural area. In both the area first preferred choice of contraceptive method was permanent method after having two children's whereas temporary contraceptive method of preference were condom, mala-D and copper -T. None of the participant were preferred other methods of contraceptive like jelly, foam tablets and injectable in urban slum and rural area.

Mao J study also stated that the respondents were having less knowledge regarding diaphragm, Jelly /foams tablets.^[9]

Preferred choice of contraceptive method were significantly associated with the demographic data of participants like age, education, type of family, no of children, years of marriage and family income.

CONCLUSION:

Above study shows that the preferred choice of contraceptive methods among married women are mala-D, copper-T and male condom. Although government has launched various awareness programs regarding use of contraceptives, the study findings indicate that women in urban and rural areas

lack information regarding female condom, injectable and other modern contraceptives methods .

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